

ANALYSIS OF RELATED THEORIES FOR CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITIES**Alhato O.***Doctoral school, Faculty of economic sciences
University December 1, 1918, of Alba Iulia, Romania***Abstract**

Corporate social responsibilities (CSR) concept establishes the importance of organizations to consider the interests of society by taking responsibility for the impact of their activities on employees, shareholders, community, and the environment in all aspects of their operation.

Research on corporate social responsibility (CSR) has experienced remarkable drive, corporate social responsibility research illustrates the role of values in guiding both mission and vision of a business organization, as well as for expressing the extent of its obligations or accountability.

In this descriptive and theoretical research paper, we conduct a systematic literature review of CSR from the point of view of various researchers. Also, In this paper, we attempt to further the theoretical debate about corporate social responsibility (CSR) by highlighting the main core theories for Corporate social responsibilities. Thereafter, the article clearly sets the stage for businesses case within its appropriate sectors on CSR or the justification why business executives may be motivated to allocate resources to engage in CSR activities.

Keywords: corporate social responsibilities (CSR), systematic literature review, stakeholders' theory, institutional theory, Legitimacy theory.

Jel classification: M 41

1. Introduction

Today Corporate social responsibilities (CSR) are universal as most large firms have entire branches committed to ensuring socially responsible practices and executing charitable activities. CSR is framed by the theories discussed in the field as a strategic tool to gain economic objectives and generate wealth and value.

Starting after the Second World War, CSR has been used but started to gain importance after the 1960s. Historically its understanding has shifted over the decades, CSR was viewed as a personal decision of managers. This changed in the 1980s when the concept developed more into a decision-making process (Tripathi and Bains 2013). In later decades of the 20th century, the focus moved away to more attention to the operationalization of the concept, and the level of analysis shifted from a macro level to an organizational level in this period.

However, since the early 2000s, it has been understood as a strategic necessity and a vital aspect of modern business (Ślęzak 2021). The interest and growth of CSR has led to voluntary initiatives in corporate social responsibility in international business in recent years and there was a significant growth in the number of indices ("benchmarks"), to describe economic situation of the companies meeting specific CSR requirements

According to Zemigala (2017), the majority of terms that do describe CSR, refers to those voluntary social and environmental aspects of an organization. These terms can be divided into two parts namely internal and external activities, Internal activities are all the pro workforce activities and external activities detailing all the actions that are addressed to partners, local community, public authorities and the ecology. CSR as companies being responsible for their impact on society by being sustainable, competitive and innovative towards the economy and individual enterprises.

2. Research methodology

Methodology adopted in this paper has applicability in areas beyond Corporate social responsibilities (CSR). a theoretical and qualitative approach was mainly adopted. The main aim of the research is to analyze and describe a general description of (CSR) practices through several theories and relevant literatures. We employed conceptual paper approach using the research conducted by Vitolla et al (2017) as a reference. this study consists the Following objectives were framed.

1- *To review the literature in according to understand the practices of corporate social responsibilities (CSR).*

2- *To describes the important theories for corporate social responsibilities for example Stakeholder's theory, institutional theory, and Legitimacy theory.*

3. Literature Review: Corporate social responsibilities theories

The literature continues to expand the theoretical understanding of CSR and its multidimensional concepts as it relates across the business background. This section considers several theoretical perspectives to explain why business management engage in CSR activities. Literature has offered us many different theories of CSR with the conception of CSR having a wider diversity of topics and many that still need to be further explored. including stakeholder theory, Legitimacy theory and institutional theory. In such, the purpose of this section is to outline these theories and highlight the similarities and differences where applicable in order to establish the research theoretical framework.

3.1 Stakeholder's theory

The stakeholder theory conceptualizes business organizations as part of a wider system wherein their operations have impact upon other individuals and groups, and wherein their operations are impacted by

other individuals and groups. These groups are suppliers, creditors, customers, competitors, employees, and the community within which the business operates. It implies the responsibilities of managers in stakeholder theory go beyond profit maximization; but they have to consider the interests of other parties who have stakes in the business activities (Murphy and Smolarski, 2020). The managers are to ensure that the ethical rights of stakeholders are balanced, not violated and to also ensure the legitimate interest of all stakeholders are put into consideration during the decision-making. In a multinational environment, the stakeholders could also include governments, activist, bankers, financiers, special interest groups, the environment, media, and technological progress forming a group of global stakeholders.

The interrelationship between stakeholder theory and Corporate social responsibilities, both CSR and stakeholder theory come as two major concepts. However, there has been little clarity so far in what relation CSR and stakeholder theory stand to each other. The main similarity between the two concepts is that both stakeholder theory and CSR stress the importance of incorporating societal interests into business operations. Businesses are embedded in society always. the two concepts differ in that stakeholder theory posits the key responsibilities of the business overall, i.e. corporate responsibilities, where responsibility to the society (which is often represented by the communities where business operates) is a very important but only one part among other corporate responsibilities. the main stake-

holders typically include employees, customers, communities, suppliers, and financiers (owners, investors). Figure (1) provides a visual illustration of the relationship between stakeholder theory and CSR. Both stakeholder theory and CSR stress the importance of company responsibility toward communities and society. However, stakeholder theory tends to center its attention within a reasonable reach of company's activities, thus focusing on local communities where the company operates (Figure (1) Freeman and Dmytriyev, 2017. inner circle that stands for primary stakeholders) and surrounding society, a bigger area where local communities reside, e.g. city or district (Figure 1 outer circle that stands for secondary stakeholders). While CSR tends to extend the social orientation of the company much further, often to its maximum. CSR mainly focuses on ethical labor practices and environmental efforts, while stakeholder theory tries to embrace company responsibilities toward these stakeholders in full, as well as the stakeholders' responsibilities towards the company and its other stakeholders (so responsibility is multi-directional). Stakeholder theory also addresses company responsibilities toward financiers and suppliers.

The various challenges in implementing CSR initiatives can be mitigated by aligning the concept with stakeholder theory as this enables leaders to have a more pragmatic approach considering the interests of all its stakeholders and planning its actions accordingly. Stakeholder theory addresses the issue of a lack of awareness of the benefits of CSR (Harrison, et al., 2019).

Figure (1) the relationship between stakeholder theory and CSR

Source: Freeman and Dmytriyev, 2017.

3.2 Legitimacy theory

Legitimacy theory has a very close relationship with corporate social responsibility because this theory explains the social contract that occurs between the community and the company. the survival of a company will be threatened if the community feels the company has violated its social contract. The theory of le-

gitimacy is based on a social contract that exists between the company and the community around the company that is active and uses economic resources. Legitimacy theory is also defined as something that companies want and seek from the community (Puji, 2019). In the theory of legitimacy, it is explained that in order to get legitimacy from the surrounding com-

munity, companies must disclose their social responsibilities. Undesirable things can be prevented by legitimacy.

Legitimacy is a generalized perception or assumption that the actions of an entity are desirable, proper within some socially constructed system of norms, values, beliefs. Scholars regard legitimacy as an operational resource that, at its heart, guarantees organizations a so-called 'license to operate,' which provides the base level of leeway necessary for an organization to decoration (Nicholas Browning et.al, 2022). Unpacking that definition further reveals key characteristics of the construct. First, legitimacy constitutes a perceived judgment as to whether organizational goals and actions align with some value system. Stakeholders make these judgments. Because legitimacy is determined not by the organization but rather by engaged communities, managing it is inherently difficult. However, that difficulty multiplies exponentially when one considers that stakeholders define and assess legitimacy in a myriad of ways, which becomes further complicated considering the power imbalances among stakeholders.

As distinct stakeholder groups make disparate judgments about legitimacy, they also make judgments about different facets of an organization, potentially conferring distinct types of legitimacy. Suchman's described three general types of legitimacy: pragmatic, moral, and cognitive. Pragmatic legitimacy is rooted in the self-interests of both the organization and its audiences. It largely reflects a stakeholder perception that an organization has effectively delivered on instrumental expectations, most commonly in the exchanges of goods and services. Moral legitimacy involves an evaluation of whether an organization supports or weakens societal welfare within a given value system. The evaluation criteria might be consequentialist (organization accomplishes desirable ends), procedural (organization follows accepted rules of conduct), structural (organization is systemically constructed to promote just action), or personal (organization and its leaders display charisma and character). These four criteria align with major programs of Western ethical thought: utilitarianism, deontology, Rawlsian justice as fairness, and Aristotelean virtue, respectively (Thompson,2022). Lastly, cognitive legitimacy, which embodies the inertial characteristic of legitimacy. At this stage, organizational actions are highly comprehensible and readily explained by easily accessible cultural norms. This creates a taken-for-granted legitimacy in which the very expectation that an organization characteristically behaves legitimately confers legitimacy to its current and future actions.

3.3 institutional theory

Institutional theory has prevailed as a dominant theoretical approach used to examine phenomena within the voluntary. Institutional theory has its origin in a wide range of different views of organized human behavior; they all share the underlying assumption that organized human behavior cannot be seen as isolated from social structure and social interactions. The perspective of institutional theory contradicts the assump-

tion of rational economic actors, who advocate that organizations (e.g., managers) are rational and always choose the most efficient and competitive alternative without considering the influence of the social environment in which they operate (Katsikas et al., 2017). Instead, institutional theory concerns aspects regarding social structures, where the relationship between organizations and their environment is in focus (Katsikas et al., 2017). The theory lies upon two underpinning assumptions; (1) The environment in which organizations interact is socially constructed. And (2) Organizations are seen as open systems allowing them to be affected by the external environment. Consequently, the structure and activities of the organizations are influenced by the conditions in the specific environment. This is because organizations seek to be considered socially norm and legitimate by the large system. In the perspective of the theory, the external environment is composed of institutions defines institutions as: comprised by regulative, normative, and cultural-cognitive elements that, together with associated activities and resources provide stability and meaning for social life. The pressures stemming from the institution influence the organizations' behavior, leading organizations within an institution to become more homogeneous. This process develops through three mechanisms of homogenization, or isomorphism: coercive, mimetic, and normative isomorphism. Coercive isomorphism concerns the regulatory pillar of the theory. The regulative pillar refers to pressures stemming from the institution's rules, laws, policies, sanctions, punishments, and recompense. By adapting or mimicking the requirement of laws, policies, or sanctions, the organization complies with these requirements and gains legitimacy. In this process, isomorphic tendencies are typically created. If the organization does not comply, it is not only seen as illegitimate but might be punished. Mimetic isomorphism concerns the cultural-cognitive pillars of the theory. The cultural-cognitive dimension refers to values, symbols, and meanings in social action within the institution. When organizations operate in uncertainty, they tend to imitate other organizations' structures, cultures, or behaviors due to that they consider the latter organization more successful or legitimate. In this process, mimetic isomorphism develops and creates homogeneity effects. Normative isomorphism concerns the normative pillars of institutional theory. In this pillar, values and norms within an institutional field are referred to Normative mechanisms are created when organizations follow the perceived expectations on the right thing to do. Organizational change is also explained to be driven by professionalization, which means that formal education and professional networks are two reasons for isomorphic effects. Through homogeneity of educational background and cooperation in professional networks, similar practices are developed both within the organization and in the external environment where they operate. Thus, the rationale of the theory is that an organization's behavior is influenced by the external pressure in the institution, leading to the adoption of certain organizational practices (Anton and Ester, 2022). Scholars advocate that what mainly influences the behavior is the surrounding institutions.

These can be regulative structures, cultural-cognitive and normative, that bring collective meaning and stability to social behavior through isomorphism processes. In this sense, an organization's behavior can be understood by investigating institutional pressures and social interaction since the behavior reflects the perspectives defined by the actors comprising the institutional environment. According to the theory, organizations are aware of their dependence on the external institution. Therefore, they embed conditions or conceptions from the institution within the organization to gain legitimacy. This adaptation of the organization's behavior has different consequences for the organization.

4. Conclusion

In this article, we systematically reviewed theories that were related to Corporate social responsibilities (CSR). Our contribution to this paper there is highlighted and elaborated on three common theories for CSR (stakeholder theory, Legitimacy theory and institutional theory). These theories of CSR are articulated in distinct ways to guide managers who may wish to reconcile their obligations to their shareholders with those to other competing groups claiming legitimacy and recognition. These theories be able to be recognized as normative theories showing managers what their responsibilities are to various regions. In addition, The Stakeholder Theory gives high attention to the economic obligation, which is the interest of shareholders to maximize corporate profits.

Within this paper two main approaches concerning (CSR) have been described; analyzing and discussing the main theories. One of the main conclusions is that these theories that the organization's activities can lead to responsible behaviors that would benefit the whole society which the corporation is effective in.

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